

Comparative study of compounds present in essential oil of two species of *Michelia*

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Manuscript received 24 July 2009, accepted 31 December 2009

Abstract : White champaka (*Michelia alba*) products are popular in the Indian market. The fragrance is widely used to produce various cosmetic products and incense sticks. The other species of genus *Michelia* is *Michelia champaka*, the golden variety champaka (swarna champa), which is also very popular in India for its beautiful fragrance and is held sacred by Hindus. The essential oil of the flower is widely used in perfumery and also as a stimulant. The volatile components present in these two species of *Michelia* were extracted by hexane and their relative compositions were examined by GC-MS analysis.

Keywords : *Michelia*, *Michelia alba*, *Michelia champaka*, GC-MS, essential oil.

Introduction

Essential oils are important natural products used in food, pharmaceutical and perfumery industries. They are also sources of important aroma chemicals and their biological and pharmacological activities had gathered momentum in recent years. Many essential oils enjoy generally recognized as safe (GRAS) status. The growing sector of aroma therapy expands the market of essential oil even more.

Michelia alba and *Michelia champaka* are the two species of genus *Michelia*, indigenous flowers of to Asia, and both are very popular to Indian people for their pleasant and beautiful aroma. *Michelia alba* (white champaka), family Magnoliaceae, is a well known fragrant flower with a gentle scent that has long been utilized by Indian people. The genus includes about fifty species of evergreen trees and shrubs native to tropical and subtropical South and South East Asia (Indomalaya) including southern China. *M. alba* flowers are the source of fragrance oil used extensively for making perfume^{1,2}. The tree producing these *M. alba* is an annual flowering plant; generally the flowers begin to bloom round 8–9 pm, with their scent becoming quickly widespread and the scent begins to fade in the afternoon. *M. alba* also acts as a cough suppressant and expectorant³. Dry *M. alba* flowers are

also used in Thai traditional medicine for heart and nerve maintenance and anti-motion sickness⁴. In addition to the encouraging pharmacological actions, *M. alba* is among the world's famous fragrant flowers; its oil is one of the common ingredients in several expensive perfumes⁵.

The other species of genus *Michelia* is *Michelia champaka*, the golden variety champaka (locally known as swarna champa) and is also very popular in India for its beautiful fragrance. The flowering is due twice a year – once in spring and other in autumn, however practically it extends from March to October. Flowers are held sacred by Hindus particularly in South India. The essential oil of the flower is widely used in perfumery, incense stick and also as a stimulant (D. P. Mukhopadhyay and R. K. Chakraborty, Plant wealth of Rajbavan, Kolkata).

There are usually several components present in any aromatic oil and their identification and quantification after extraction is a critical study. Steam distillation, solvent extraction, enfleurage methods are the common methods for extraction of volatile oils from aromatic plants^{5,6}. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) is a useful tool for qualitative and quantitative analysis for volatile compounds and is used widely in biological and medicinal researches^{7–9}.

The objective of this study was to compare the oil composition of these two flowers of the genus *Michelia*, *Michelia alba*, the white variety and *Michelia champaka*, the golden variety (locally known as swarna champaka). The oils were extracted by solvent extraction method and the chemical composition of the oils were analyzed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry method.

Results and discussion

Chemical composition of M. alba extract in hexane :

The chemical profiles of the oil, the amount of the individual components, and gas chromatographic and mass spectral data are summarised in Table 1 and the gas chromatogram is shown in Fig. 1. The oil extract contains linalool (2.068%), verbenol (1.582%), octadecane (3.317%), caryophyllene (4.8%) but the major compounds detected were isogeraniol (18.22%) and isopulegol acetate (21.17%) (Table 1).

Chemical composition of M. champaka extract in hexane :

The chemical profiles of the oil, the amount (%) of the individual components, and gas chromatographic and mass spectral data are summarised in Table 1 and the gas chromatogram is shown in Fig. 2. 15 compounds were identified with full certainty and these were linalool, 2*H*-pyran-3-ol, 6-ethynyl tetrahydro-2,2,6-trimethyl, neral/geranial, indole, beta-pinene, alpha-methyl-alpha-[4-methyl-3-pentenyl] oxirane methanol, phenyl ethyl alcohol, nerol/geraniol, benzoic acid-2-amino methyl ester, benzoic acid-4-ethoxy ethyl ester, octadecane, 7,9-ditert-butyl-1-oxaspiro (4,5) deca, 6,9-diene-2,8-dione, and the major compounds detected were bornyl salicylate and caryophyllene.

In most European flowers the common aroma components are linalool, nerol, geraniol etc. Linalool is known as important attractant for many insects and is used in perfumery industries as essential component in optimum concentration. Researchers from Thailand reported that *M. alba* extract of Thailand contains 28.92% linalool in hexane extract². But in Indian variety we found only 2.06%

Table 1. Some of the aroma components present in two varieties of Champaka (*M. champaka* and *M. alba*) obtained from GC-MS study

Sl. no.	R _i	Compds.	Molecular weight	Molecular formula	<i>M. alba</i> extract (% w/w)	<i>M. champaka</i> extract (% w/w)
1.	9.939	Beta-pinene	136	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	tr	0.181
2.	10.256	Alpha-methyl-alpha-[4-methyl-3-pentenyl]oxiranemethanol	170	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O ₂	tr	0.266
3.	11.25	Linalool	154	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	2.068	2.241
4.	11.58	Phenyl ethyl alcohol	122	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	0.704	0.2875
5.	12.51	2 <i>H</i> -Pyran-3-ol,6-ethenyl tetrahydro 2,2,6-trimethyl	170	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O ₂	0.48	3.206
6.	13.56	Verbenol	152	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	1.582	-
7.	13.71	Isogeraniol	154	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	18.22	-
8.	13.99	Neral/geranial	152	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	2.775	2.60
9.	14.39	Nerol/geraniol	154	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	tr	0.695
10.	14.57	Indole	117	C ₈ H ₇ N	0.3719	1.448
11.	15.17	Benzoic acid-2-amino methyl ester	151	C ₈ H ₉ NO ₂	-	0.414
12.	15.49	Bornyl salicylate	274	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₃	-	19.63
13.	15.49	Isopulegol acetate	196	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂	21.17	-
14.	16.20	Caryophyllene	204	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	4.80	6.585
15.	17.46	Benzoic acid-4-ethoxy ethyl ester	194	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₃	3.0194	2.98
16.	19.36	Octadecane	254	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	3.317	1.54
17.	21.92	7,9-Ditert-butyl 1-oxaspiro (4,5) deca 6,9-diene-2,8-dione	276	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₃	0.53	0.259
18.	24.32	Linoleic acid methyl ester	294	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂	-	1.16

Fig. 1. Gas-Chromatogram of hexane extract of the flower *Michelia alba*.

linalool content where as isogeraniol (18.22%) and isopulegol acetate (21.17%) were present as major components. Indole usually plays the role of fixative in perfumery compositions which increases the perceived odor strength and improves the stability of the other components in volatile oil. As per our analysis, indole content of the oil of *M. alba* and *M. champaka* were 0.37% and 1.448% respectively. The comparison of the volatile compounds present in two species showed *M. champaka* oil extract contained an unusual component, bornyl salicy-

late (19.63%), which has a herbal note and reported to be present in lemon and mint oil¹⁰. This compound was absent in the oil of white champaka and may be responsible for the characteristic odour of swarnachampa flower.

Experimental

Materials :

Collection of flowers : *M. champaka* and *M. alba*, both are seasonal flowers. Flowers were collected from

Fig. 2. Gas-Chromatogram of hexane extract of the flower *Michelia champaka*.

the tree of different places, Garden of Alipore Horticultural Society, Kolkata and village gardens in the month of their full blooming condition.

Methods :

Extraction and separation of aroma components : The fresh flowers were immersed in HPLC grade hexane for

minimum 2 h at room temperature and then the hexane layer was separated. The solvent layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for analysis. The presence of aromatic components in hexane layer was confirmed by taking the extract on filter paper and sniffing after evaporation of hexane.

Analysis of chemical composition of oil samples using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) : A Varian Saturn 2200 GC-MS instrument equipped with DB-5 capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm film thickness) was used for component analysis. The oven temperature was maintained at 50 °C for 5 min, and then programmed to 200 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹. Final temperature was 280 °C at 5 °C min⁻¹ and maintained for 20 min. The carrier gas was helium at a flow rate of 0.9 mL min⁻¹, and the injection volume was 1 µL. In mass spectrometry, the electron-impact ionization was performed of electron energy 70 eV. The samples were analysed in triplicate set and the mean data are presented.

Compound identification : Components of the oil were identified by comparison of their mass spectra and retention indices with those published in the literature⁹ and contained in the NBS/NIST computer libraries.

Acknowledgement

The financial support for this work was given by University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India. We acknowledge the kind help of Prof. S. Roy, University of Calcutta for helping in interpreting the GC-MS results

and Dr. Tapas Saha and Dr. Suparna Sen of SGS Analytical Services, Kolkata for GC-MS analysis.

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